

Soil and Crop Management

Mollisol productivity under two management levels

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We studied the productivity of a Mollisol occupying the lowest position on a 0-1% slope and developed on fine silty calcareous alluvial parent material. The profile was poorly drained. Surface and subsurface texture was clay loam, subsoil texture varied from silt loam to silty clay loam (Table 1). The soil was classified as fine silty, mixed, hyperthermic Typic Haplaquoll. It belongs to the Phoolbagh series.

A crop management experiment was conducted on this soil during the 1983 rainy season. High and moderate management levels were applied in a randomized block design with four replications.

High management approximated the practices followed by affluent and progressive farmers of the area. It included summer plowing, harrowing, and leveling; optimum transplanting (around 15 Jul), maintaining 3-5 cm water level in the field: 120 kg N and

Table 1. Physical and chemical properties of soil at Pantnagar, India, 1983.

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	pH	Organic matter (%)	CaCO ₃ equivalent (%)	Cation exchange capacity (meq/100 g)	Base saturation (%)
Ap	0-11	44	24	32	7.8	3.2	0.4	25.2	91
A ₁	11-31	43	21	36	7.9	2.6	0.7	24.6	91
A ₃	31-48	45	31	24	8.0	2.0	0.7	19.1	100
B ₂	48-10	42	37	21	8.0	1.5	2.1	17.6	95
HB ₃	70-90	25	36	39	8.1	1.4	2.5	13.5	100
IIC	90-96+	24	41	35	8.1	1.2	2.6	13.2	98

Table 2. Yield components and yield, and net income^a under 2 management levels. Pantnagar, India, 1983.

Management level	Tillers/meter (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Harvest index	Gross income (\$)	Production cost (\$)	Net income (\$)
High	64	5.9	7.9	43	786.83	315.31	411.52
Moderate	53 ^b	5.0 ^b	6.3	44	664.87	229.95	434.92

^aUS\$1 = Indian rupees 10.50 (Nov 1983). ^bSignificant difference at 5% level.

40 kg P/ha; and weeding at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting.

Moderate management was a combination of practices followed by a farmer with moderate resources and know-how. It included summer plowing, harrowing, and leveling; late transplanting around 21 Jul, maintaining field moisture at saturation; 60 kg N and 20 kg P/ha; and weeding at 20 and 40 d after transplanting.

N was applied as urea in three split

doses and P as single superphosphate as a basal dose. Diseases and pests were controlled as needed.

Number of tillers and grain yield were significantly higher under high level of management (Table 2). The significant increase in grain yield was due to more effective tillers per unit area.

But net income was somewhat lower under high management level because of increased costs of production. □

Effect of nitrogen source and insect control on growth of a ratoon crop

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We studied N source and insecticide treatment on a ratoon crop (Sona Mahsuri) in 1985-86. The area has endemic brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* that could survive in the stubble of a ratoon crop. There were 4 fertilizer treatments: 0 N/ha, 50 kg N/ha, azolla applied 34 times at 2.5 t/ha, and azolla + 25 kg N/ha. The insecticides were

monocrotophos at 0.5 kg ai/ha and chlorpyrifos at 0.3 kg ai/ha. Treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Azolla (fresh weight) was applied on the soil surface 3-4 times, up to 12 t/ha. But the azolla could not be uniformly maintained in the field. Growth and multiplication were retarded by fluctuating water level, snail damage, and high temperature. Soil salinity also could have affected azolla growth. Soils were black deep Vertisols with pH 8.5. N content of the azolla was about 6%.

Regenerated tillers were counted at 15

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